

ParserHunter: Identify Parsing Functions in Binary Code

Marco Scapin^a, Fabio Pinelli^a, Letterio Galletta^a

^aIMT School for Advanced Studies Lucca, Lucca, Italy

Abstract

Parsing and validation functions are crucial because they process untrusted data, e.g., user inputs. Due to their complexity, these functions are highly susceptible to bugs, making them a primary target for security audits. However, identifying such functions within a binary is time-intensive and challenging, given the numerous functions typically present and the lack of source code or supporting documentation. This paper presents an AI-based methodology for identifying functions with parser-like behavior and complex processing logic within a binary. Our methodology analyzes each binary by identifying its functions, extracting their Control Flow Graphs (CFGs), and enriching them with features derived from an embedding model that captures both structural and semantic aspects of their behavior. These annotated CFGs are the input to a Graph Neural Network trained to identify parsing functions. We implement this methodology in the tool ParserHunter, which allows users to train the model on labeled data, query the model with unseen binaries, and accommodate a symbolic execution phase on the processed binary through a user interface. Our experiments on ten real-world projects from GitHub show that our tool effectively identifies parsers in binaries.

Keywords: Binary analysis, Function Identification, Graph Neural Network.

1. Introduction

Binary code analysis is crucial in security auditing, as it facilitates the understanding and assessment of software behavior without access to its source code. This activity is particularly relevant when analyzing proprietary or legacy software, or more generally, in all situations where the source code is unavailable. As a preliminary step, this type of security auditing often requires a reverse engineering phase, where experts disassemble or decompile the binary and manually analyze the recovered code to understand the software's behavior and identify specific parts of the code that can be interesting targets for deeper analysis or fuzzing campaigns. Typically, security analysts focus their efforts on those functions responsible for critical operations, e.g., reading data from the network, managing private resources, or those that are more prone to vulnerabilities, e.g., buffer overflow. Among these, parsing and validation functions play a crucial role. Indeed, these functions process untrusted data, such as user inputs or network packets, and implement complex logic to interpret and manipulate this data [1, 2]. Due to their complexity, parsing and validation functions are highly susceptible to bugs: weaknesses in input validation are one of the leading causes of software security vulnerabilities, according to Mitre's Top 25 Most Dangerous Software Weaknesses list [3]. The problem is especially serious in low-level or embedded software, where a single missing check can compromise the entire software stack. This makes parsing and validation functions a focal target for security auditing [4]. However, identifying such functions is a time-intensive and challenging task, given the large number of functions typically present within a binary and the lack of source code or supporting documentation. Automating this process can significantly improve the ef-

iciency and accuracy of software audits, providing crucial support to expert analysts.

The scientific literature abounds with research addressing various aspects of binary analysis, such as binary function similarity, vulnerability analysis, and function identification [5, 6, 7, 8]. However, to the best of our knowledge, only a few papers specifically tackle the complex challenge of identifying parser functions [2]. Additionally, several factors motivate the need for methodologies and tools to identify such functions. First, many approaches designed for related problems are unsuitable for parser identification. This is because they often build highly specialized frameworks tailored to specific research questions, limiting their adaptability to broader contexts. Additionally, these methods often rely on manually selected features, such as the presence and frequency of specific instructions, which, although effective for their intended tasks, lack the generalizability necessary to apply the framework or model to other function classification problems. Second, these approaches often result in analysis tools that rely on proprietary software to implement certain functionalities. The use of proprietary components can prevent users without a license from directly using the tool, and may even require re-implementing essential functionalities from scratch, limiting the accessibility and adaptability of the results. These gaps underscore the need for a novel and adaptable approach to this problem, one that is supported by open-source tools.

This paper aims to fill this gap and present an AI-based methodology, supported by the tool ParserHunter for identifying functions with parser-like behavior and complex processing logic within a binary code. The proposed approach is designed to be highly customizable, enabling adaptability by modifying the labeled data or adjusting individual steps of the process. By

automating this process, ParserHunter enables faster and more accurate identification of critical functions, streamlining the auditing workflow for reverse engineering experts.

More precisely, as a preliminary step, we define a set of criteria that characterize when a piece of code may exhibit complex logic or behavior similar to that of a parser. We use these criteria to drive the labeling of our training data. Once we have defined what characteristics a parser function must possess, our methodology develops as follows. First, we analyze each binary file, identify each function therein, and extract its Control Flow Graph (CFG). The CFG is then enriched with features that capture structural and contextual information relevant to the function’s behavior, obtaining what we call an Attribute CFG (ACFG). These ACFGs form the input for the training phase, using a deep learning model based on a Graph Neural Network (GNN), a class of neural network particularly well-suited for processing graph-structured data. GNNs can learn complex relationships within graphs, as highlighted by previous studies [6], which underscore the value of semantic graph representations, such as CFGs, for addressing various tasks in binary analysis. Our methodology also involves a model selection step based on a grid search procedure to select the best model and its corresponding hyperparameters. By integrating these steps, our experiments show that we provide a robust and extensible methodology for parser identification in binary code.

This methodology is implemented in the tool ParserHunter, which has two main functionalities. The first allows users to train, validate, and test a GNN model to recognize parsing functions on a set of functions extracted from binaries, labeled with the corresponding class (i.e., parser/non-parser). The second is a web application that allows users to upload binary executables and detect parser functions within them, applying the best model. Additionally, the web interface includes functionalities to facilitate the symbolic execution of classified functions, thereby accommodating the overall binary auditing workflow. We experimentally assess the tool identification capabilities on real-world case studies, showing the model’s effectiveness and generalizability.

In summary, the main contributions of this paper are:

- We propose, to the best of our knowledge, the first set of criteria for classifying a function as a parser from its code, which may drive and support the preparation and labeling of a dataset.
 - We present a flexible and adaptable methodology to identify and extract functions from a binary as an ACFG and use them to train a GNN to solve the parser identification task. This methodology is flexible and can be easily adapted to other tasks.
 - We implement this methodology within the tool ParserHunter: it permits users to train, validate, and test their GNN on a dataset and use a trained model to identify parser functions inside new binaries. Moreover, it provides facilities that help security analysts accommodate the symbolic execution of the identified functions.
- We experimentally train and evaluate ParserHunter on ten real-world GitHub projects, showing its effectiveness in identifying parser functions. We study the robustness of our model to the various optimizations a compiler may perform on a binary. We compare the prediction performances of our model against previous approaches from the literature, standard machine learning techniques, and techniques based on modern large language models. Our experiments demonstrate that our model outperforms all others when recall is the primary evaluation metric.

In the rest of the paper, we proceed as follows. Section 2 provides relevant background information to facilitate an understanding of our technical development. In Section 3, we introduce the details of our methodology, while in Section 4, we present the internals of ParserHunter, and describe how we select the best model. Section 5 explains how we train our model, evaluate our tool’s classification performance according to well-known metrics, and compare it against several baselines. In Section 6, we compare our work with the relevant literature, while in Section 7, we draw some conclusions and discuss some future lines of investigation.

Code and data availability: The code of the tool, the datasets, and the scripts used for our experiments are available online [9].

2. Background

Here, we briefly review some background concepts about program representation and GNN, which our methodology for identifying parsing functions relies on.

Program representation. We use the notion of a control flow graph (CFG) as a data structure to represent the code and all possible paths of program execution. The nodes of such a graph are basic blocks. A *basic block* is a sequence of contiguous assembly instructions with a single entry and exit point and represents a segment of code executed sequentially. The first instruction of a basic block is a jump target, while the last one is a jump or branch instruction. Moreover, each basic block is typically identified by a unique label used to jump to its first instruction. Formally, a *Control Flow Graph* $G = (V, E)$ is a directed graph where V represents the basic blocks of the program, and E are edges indicating possible control flow transitions between them. More precisely, an edge between basic blocks b_1 and b_2 means that the execution may be transferred from b_1 to b_2 at run-time. The CFG captures the structure and some semantic information about the behavior of a piece of code, which is critical for our task of identifying parsing functions.

Graph Neural Network. Graph Neural Networks [10] (GNNs) are a class of neural network architectures specifically designed to operate on graph-structured data. GNNs learn representations of nodes, edges, or entire graphs by leveraging the relational structure between nodes. A typical GNN model follows a message-passing framework, where node features are iteratively updated based on messages aggregated from neighbors.

A typical GNN layer consists of two parts: the *message* and *update* layer. In the *message* layer, each node receives information from its neighbors and aggregates it to capture the local graph structure. Formally, given a node v with neighbors $\mathcal{N}(v)$, the aggregated message $m_v^{(k)}$ at layer k is computed as:

$$m_v^{(k)} = M\left(\left\{h_u^{(k-1)} \mid u \in \mathcal{N}(v)\right\}\right)$$

where $h_u^{(k-1)}$ denotes the feature vector of a neighboring node u from the previous layer. The specific message function M aggregating neighbors’ data depends on the particular GNN architecture (e.g., mean, sum, max, or a learnable function).

In the *update* layer, the aggregated message $m_v^{(k)}$ is then used to update the node’s representation. The update rule for each node v at layer k is given by:

$$h_v^{(k)} = U\left(h_v^{(k-1)}, m_v^{(k)}\right)$$

where $h_v^{(k)}$ represents the updated feature vector of node v . The update function U often includes a learnable transformation, such as a linear layer, followed by a non-linear activation. For graph classification tasks, the GNN architecture also includes a so-called readout function R that combines the representations of nodes to form a single graph-level representation H_G . It captures the structural and feature-based information of the entire graph and represents the connection between the GNN’s message-passing process and the downstream task of graph classification. The readout function R can be a simple aggregation function (i.e., sum, max, average), attention pooling, or a more advanced method.

Thus, H_G is provided as input to a classification head, typically a fully connected layer followed by a softmax activation, to produce label prediction probabilities.

Different GNN architectures employ distinct aggregation and update mechanisms tailored to specific graph structures and learning settings. In this work, we consider four message-passing architectures: the Graph Convolutional Network (GCN), the Graph Attention Network (GAT), GraphSAGE, and the Relational Graph Convolutional Network (R-GCN). Although all of them follow the general message-passing paradigm, they differ in how neighborhood information is aggregated, weighted, and normalized. GCN applies a fixed, degree-normalized aggregation scheme shared across all edges, whereas GAT relies on a learned attention mechanism to dynamically weight neighboring nodes. GraphSAGE introduces sampling-based neighborhood aggregation combined with learnable aggregators (e.g., mean, pooling, or LSTM), enabling inductive generalization to previously unseen nodes. R-GCN extends the GCN formulation to multi-relational graphs by learning relation-specific transformation matrices and performing relation-aware message aggregation with a distinct normalization strategy for each relation. In our setting, however, the underlying graph contains a single edge type, and the R-GCN is instantiated with the number of relations set to one. Despite this, R-GCN does not collapse to a standard GCN, as it retains its relation-specific parameterization and normalization scheme, which differ from those of GCN. In our experiments, we evaluate all four architectures

under the same training and evaluation protocol. For further details on these models, we refer the reader to the relevant literature [11, 12, 13, 14].

Learning Representations for Assembly Code. Learning vector representations (embeddings) for program elements is a key step in enabling machine learning models to work with code. Embedding models map code parts – such as functions or basic blocks – into numerical vectors. These vectors provide a compact representation of program behavior, allowing downstream models to compare, classify, or analyze code more effectively than raw token sequences or static features. In our pipeline, embeddings provide rich semantic features for each node in the control flow graph (CFG), complementing the graph structure and enabling graph-based models to capture both local and contextual program information. By representing CFG nodes with embeddings, our method leverages structural and semantic information simultaneously, improving the expressiveness of the input for downstream analysis tasks. In our experiments, we evaluate two embedding methods, Asm2Vec [15] and SAFE [16], which we briefly introduce below, and assess the performance of our pipeline while using them.

Asm2Vec. Asm2Vec [15] is a neural embedding technique designed specifically for assembly code. It captures both the syntactic structure and semantic behavior of instructions, producing embeddings that reflect function-level execution patterns. The model considers the hierarchical structure of functions and the flow of control between instructions, generating a sequence of instruction-level embeddings that are recursively aggregated into a single vector per function or basic block. This approach preserves control flow and execution semantics, making Asm2Vec particularly suitable for CFG-level analysis. In our pipeline, Asm2Vec provides feature representations for CFG nodes, enriching the graph structure with semantic context.

SAFE. SAFE (*Self-Attentive Function Embeddings*) [16] is a recent approach to generating embeddings for binary functions. SAFE first constructs instruction embeddings using an adapted skip-gram model (i2v) and then applies a self-attention mechanism to derive function embeddings. This allows the model to capture dependencies and contextual relationships between instructions across a function. SAFE embeddings are architecture-specific and typically higher-dimensional (e.g., 100 dimensions), providing a dense representation that can be directly utilized for tasks such as function similarity or classification. In our work, we use SAFE both as an alternative to Asm2Vec for CFG node embeddings and as a baseline for generating function-level embeddings.

3. Identification Methodology

This section presents our methodology for identifying parser functions within binaries. Our approach is partly inspired by Pradel and Chandra’s framework [17], which provides valuable insights into neural methods for software analysis. First, we introduce a set of criteria that a code segment must satisfy to be

considered as a parser. Then, we formalize the machine learning task our pipeline addresses.

3.1. Requirements to be a parsing function

According to some work in the literature [18], any code that manipulates input data may potentially be a parser. This notion is broad enough to encompass both parsers used by compilers and interpreters, as well as those used to decode binary data in network protocols. We aim to characterize when a piece of code exhibits a parser behavior, providing a set of inclusive criteria to capture the most relevant cases. The rationale behind the selection of our criteria follows.

Intuitively, a parser is a recognizer for a given language that accepts a sequence of symbols (*a string*) if it belongs to the language, otherwise, it rejects it. Many parsers provide yes/no answers and typically build some data structure representing the accepted string. For example, in a compiler, the parser produces an abstract syntax tree of the program, whereas a parser for a network protocol produces some data type representing the received messages. The alphabet and the language depend on the specific case; however, we assume that each symbol is represented by a byte, so a string is a sequence of bytes. Thus, the final goal of a parser is to analyze this unstructured sequence of bytes to detect the expected structure in the data. Typically, a parser is implemented as a state machine. States encode parts of the input that have already been seen, whereas transitions cause the machine to move to a new state when reading a new symbol.

All that said, we define the following requirements, dubbed *IIDDOC*,¹ to identify when a piece of code exhibits a parser-like behavior. Our criteria are summarized in Table 1, and we provide brief comments on them. The first requirement is *Input Handling*, meaning that the code should use a pointer to a buffer or a file descriptor, such as a socket, and read data byte by byte. The *Internal State* requirement is met when the code maintains a state variable in memory that is updated according to the input and not returned as output. This variable stores the current state of the state machine implementing the parser. A piece of code satisfies the *Decision-Making* requirement when its control flow is driven by its input and its internal state, so capturing the transition function of a typical state machine. The *Data Structure Creation* requirement is satisfied when the code builds a data structure from the input while processing it, thus capturing the behavior of a parser that constructs some representation of its valid input. The *Outcome* requirement requests a piece of code to return either a boolean value or some data structure to denote the successful processing of the input. Finally, a piece of code satisfies the *Compositionality* requirement when its behavior is defined in terms of other code that is a parser. This is common when a parser is implemented following a recursive descent approach, where a procedure is defined for each nonterminal symbol of the grammar. When a production rule is defined as a composition of other productions, then

Table 1: IIDDOC Requirements for Parser Identification

Req	Description
I	<i>Input Handling</i> : The code deals with a pointer to a buffer of bytes or a file descriptor for reading unstructured data.
I	<i>Internal State</i> : The code maintains an internal state in memory to represent the parsing state that is not returned as output.
D	<i>Decision-Making</i> : The code takes decisions based on the input and the internal state.
D	<i>Data Structure Creation</i> : The code builds a data structure representing the accepted input or executes specific actions on it.
O	<i>Outcome</i> : The code returns either a boolean value or a data structure built from the parsed data indicating the outcome of the recognition.
C	<i>Compositionality</i> : The code behavior is defined as a composition of other parsers.

the corresponding parser is likewise defined compositionally. Thus, our requirement tries to capture these situations.

In summary, we define a function to be a parser when it satisfies the first five requirements of Table 1 or if it is defined in terms of other parser functions, thus satisfying the requirement *Compositionality*. These requirements serve as our guidelines and drive the labeling process of our training dataset.

We now present two code examples to illustrate how our requirements apply in practice. For clarity of presentation, the examples are written in the C programming language. Figure 1 shows a simple function to parse an email address: it scans an input string character-by-character and determines the username (local-part) and the domain name. The function satisfies the first five requirements listed in Table 1. Specifically, the first three requirements are met because the function takes as input the parameter `email`, which points to the unstructured data to be analyzed; it maintains the parsing state in the local variable `state` (line 7); and the control flow within the `while` loop (line 10) is determined by both `email` and `state`. Furthermore, the function satisfies the fourth and fifth requirements: during the analysis of the input inside the `while` loop, the relevant characters are used to populate the fields of the structure `addr`, which represent the two components of the address. Finally, the function returns a boolean value to indicate if the parsing succeeds, while the parameter `addr` serves as an output containing the result of the parsing.

Figure 2 presents another function for parsing an email address, illustrating how the *Compositionality* requirement is fulfilled. Specifically, it relies on the auxiliary functions `parse_local` and `parse_domain`, which independently satisfy the IIDDOC requirements (we omit their code for brevity). In this setting, `parse_email` is itself a parser, but one that is constructed by composing other parsers.

¹The nomenclature IIDDOC is a designation we have assigned for clarity and is not an established term in the existing literature.

```

1  typedef enum {
2      STATE_LOCAL, STATE_DOMAIN,
3      STATE_DONE, STATE_ERROR
4  } State;
5
6  int parse_email(const char * email, Address * addr) {
7      State state = STATE_LOCAL;
8      size_t i = 0, local_len = 0, domain_len = 0;
9
10     while (email[i] != '\0' && state != STATE_ERROR &&
11            state != STATE_DONE) {
12         char c = email[i];
13         switch (state) {
14             case STATE_LOCAL:
15                 if (c == '@') {
16                     if (local_len == 0) {
17                         state = STATE_ERROR;
18                         break;
19                     }
20                     addr -> local[local_len] = '\0';
21                     state = STATE_DOMAIN;
22                 } else {
23                     addr -> local[local_len++] = c;
24                 }
25                 break;
26
27             case STATE_DOMAIN:
28                 if (c == '@') { // invalid: multiple @
29                     state = STATE_ERROR;
30                 } else {
31                     addr -> domain[domain_len++] = c;
32                 }
33                 break;
34
35             default:
36                 break;
37         }
38         i++;
39     }
40
41     if (state == STATE_DOMAIN) {
42         if (domain_len == 0) state = STATE_ERROR;
43         else {
44             addr -> domain[domain_len] = '\0';
45             state = STATE_DONE;
46         }
47     }
48
49     return state == STATE_DONE; // 1 success, 0 fail
50 }

```

Figure 1: A C function that parses email addresses. The code of this function satisfies the first 5 requirements of Table 1.

3.2. Problem definition

Here, we formalize the problem of identifying parsers in binaries as a classification problem. We introduce an identification pipeline comprising four main stages. The first two involve no machine learning model, the others use machine learning for computing the code embedding and for the actual classification. More precisely, we proceed as follows.

In the first stage, we analyze and disassemble each binary, identify its functions, and compute their addresses. More precisely, let B be a set of input binaries, F be the set of all possible functions, and A be the set of memory addresses. We define a function extraction procedure $E: B \rightarrow \wp(F \times A)$ as:

$$E(b) = \{(f, a) \mid f \in b \text{ and } a \text{ is the address of } f\}. \quad (1)$$

This procedure returns the set of functions defined in b along with their memory addresses. A possible implementation of E is presented in the next section.

```

1  int parse_local(const char **s, char *local) {
2      // The implementation respects IIDDOC requirements
3  }
4
5  int parse_domain(const char **s, char *domain) {
6      // The implementation respects IIDDOC requirements
7  }
8
9  int parse_email(const char *email, Address * addr){
10     return parse_local(&email, addr->local) &&
11            parse_domain(&email, addr->domain);
12 }

```

Figure 2: A C function that parses email addresses relying on two other auxiliary parsers. The code of this function satisfies the compositionality requirement of Table 1.

In the second stage, from the results of E , we perform symbolic execution to reconstruct the CFG $G_f = (V_f, E_f)$ of each function f . This step is challenging because the targets of branch and jump instructions in the assembly code may be addresses computed at run-time, so we must over-approximate them to compute the potential targets and build the CFG. Note that the recovered information is crucial as CFGs capture the code’s structural and semantic properties, offering insights into the function’s logic and flow. Formally, let $\mathcal{F} = \bigcup_{b \in B} E(b)$ be the set of all functions and addresses extracted from the binaries in B , CFG be the set of all possible CFGs, and let $\llbracket _ \rrbracket: A \rightarrow CFG$ be an abstract semantic function that, given the address a of a function f computes its CFG. We then define the set of all CFGs extracted from the functions in \mathcal{F} as

$$\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{F}} = \bigcup_{(f,a) \in \mathcal{F}} \llbracket a \rrbracket.$$

In the third stage, we enrich these CFGs by embedding semantic information into each node (basic block). We extract a set of *node features* that characterize the corresponding basic block’s behavior and summarize its instructions’ semantics. We call this enriched CFG an Attribute CFG (ACFG) [6]. Formally, let $\mathcal{H}_f: V_f \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ be a function that assigns m -dimensional feature vector to each basic block. This function employs methods such as Asm2Vec and SAFE to compute such feature vectors. Then, the set of ACFG of our input is defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{F}}^a = \bigcup_{(V_f, E_f) \in \mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{F}}} (V_f, E_f, \mathcal{H}_f).$$

In the last stage, we define our classification problem as finding a function $C: \mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{F}}^a \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ that maps each $G_f^a \in \mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{F}}^a$ to 1 if the corresponding function f exhibits a parser-like behavior and to 0 otherwise. We use a GNN as a classifier that operates on the ACFGs. The GNN processes each G_f^a by propagating information across its structure. The nodes (basic blocks) are associated with the corresponding feature vectors $\mathbf{x}_v = \mathcal{H}_f(v) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ for each node $v \in V_f$.

At each layer l of the GNN, the embeddings $h_v^{(l)}$ of node v are updated using a message passing function M and an update function U as follows:

$$m_v^{(l)} = M\left(\left\{h_u^{(l-1)} \mid u \in \mathcal{N}(v)\right\}\right)$$

$$h_v^{(l)} = U(h_v^{(l-1)}, m_v^{(l)})$$

where $m_v^{(l)}$ is the aggregated message for node v . We denote the initial features for v as $h_v^{(0)} = x_v$ where x_v is the embedding computed by Asm2Vec or SAFE.

After L layers, we obtain the final node embeddings $h_v^{(L)}$. To obtain a graph-level representation h_f for a given ACFG, we apply a readout function R that aggregates the embeddings of each node v :

$$h_f = R\left(\left\{h_v^{(L)} \mid v \in V_f\right\}\right).$$

This function could be a permutation-invariant function like summation, mean, or max pooling. Finally, we define our classification function $C: \mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{F}}^a \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ as:

$$C(G_f^a) \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \phi(h_f) \geq \tau \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

where h_f is the graph-level representation of G_f^a , $\phi(h_f) \in [0, 1]$ is the predicted probability that function f is a parser and τ is a threshold, e.g., $\tau = 0.5$.

4. ParserHunter Implementation

ParserHunter [9] is an open-source implementation of the identification pipeline of Section 3.2. The tool comprises four phases shown in Figure 3: *data preprocessing*, *embedding model usage*, *model training and validation*, and *model inference*. The first two phases serve as preparatory steps for the latter two.

Data preprocessing involves augmenting and labeling a dataset for training a machine learning model. The embedding model usage employs an embedding model (Asm2vec in Section 4.1.1 or SAFE in Section 4.1.2) to generate robust embedding vectors for the basic blocks extracted from the CFG of a given function.

Given the outputs of the previous phases, the model training and validation phase implements the definitions of Section 3.2 using a Grid Search with Cross-Validation procedure: it extracts the list of functions, computes their corresponding ACFGs, and employs a specific training and validation procedure for GNN designed to prevent data leakage, outputting an accurate machine-learning model. The final model inference phase enables end-users to interact with the trained model using their binaries through a user-friendly web interface. Below, we detail each phase.

4.1. Data Preprocessing

This phase aims to create a suitable dataset to train our classifier. Identifying parser functions within binary executables presents a significant challenge, largely due to the lack of labeled datasets crafted explicitly for this task. Since we could not rely on an existing dataset, we created one as follows. We collected ten C-based libraries and tools from GitHub, including functions implementing a parser for several data formats, from XML, JSON, ELF binaries, and the HTTP protocol. The first column of Table 2 lists the parsing libraries and tools we consider in our experiments.

We thoroughly analyzed their source code and computed the corresponding control flow graphs (CFGs), and then we annotated each function as parser or non-parser according to the

Table 2: Distribution of functions per parser library.

Library	Execs	Parsers	Non-Parsers
PicoHTTPparser [19]	28	334	426
CSimpleJSONParser [20]	28	184	469
Benoitc_HTTP [21]	28	95	326
CParserXML [22]	28	204	158
cJSON_Parser [23]	28	260	2,033
Yacc Calculator [24]	10	29	223
PCAP Parser [25]	28	28	266
Network-packet-analyzer [26]	28	56	326
Packcc [27]	28	558	1,244
ELF-parser [28]	28	229	450
Tot.	262	1977	5921

criteria reported in Table 1. We conducted the annotation process as a joint effort of the research team. Due to the technical specificity of the task, we preferred to collaboratively examine and discuss all the functions, reaching consensus on the final labels. Consequently, no inter-annotator agreement was computed, as the adopted consensus-based procedure inherently ensured a coherent interpretation of the criteria and consistent labeling across the dataset. Notice that the functions to be annotated correspond to all those contained in the source code, namely, 399 functions. Note that, following other works [6] in the literature, functions irrelevant to our classification task, such as library calls, system calls, or smaller functions (e.g., those whose CFG has fewer than three nodes), were excluded from our training data. We also excluded 13 functions where we observed that `angr` was unable to extract the assembly code.

To increase dataset diversity and improve model robustness across different compilation settings, each library was compiled using both GCC and Clang compilers using various optimization levels (O0, O1, O2, O3, Os, and OFast) and architectures, namely, x86-32 and x86-64. This compilation strategy aligns with established practices in similar studies [6]. This process produced 28 unique compiled executables for all the libraries except for YACC Calculator, where only 10 binaries were generated due to machine compatibility issues on the x86-32 architecture. In summary, a total of 262 compiled files were generated for a total of 7,898 functions, of which 1,977 were labeled as parser functions. Table 2 summarizes the functions extracted from each compiled binary, including all compilation variations. To ensure consistency across different compilations, we use function names to maintain the connection between functions and preserve their labels.

4.1.1. Asm2Vec Training

We train Asm2Vec to generate embeddings for the assembly code of basic blocks implementing the mapping function $\mathcal{H}_f: V_f \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ of Section 3.2. Using `angr` [29], we extract basic blocks from 262 object files of the ten training libraries and from 14 common Linux tools (`echo`, `grep`, `fgrep`, `egrep`, `netstat`, `ping`, `ping6`, `zcat`, `ifconfig`, `vconfig`, `awk`, `curl`, `hexdump`, `mii_mgr`), yielding approximately 693,100 basic blocks

Figure 3: The figure shows the pipeline adopted by ParserHunter to train and test a classifier to detect parser functions in binary executables.

and 2.82 million assembly instructions. We preprocess instructions by replacing numeric constants with INT and memory addresses with ADDR, reducing vocabulary size and improving generalization. After preprocessing, the vocabulary contains 454 unique tokens. The Asm2Vec model is trained with an embedding dimension of 10, a window size of 10, a minimum word frequency of 1, and over 200 epochs.

4.1.2. SAFE

SAFE [16] is used both as an alternative to Asm2Vec for CFG node embeddings and as a baseline for function-level embeddings. We use the pretrained SAFE models for AMD64 and ARM provided by the authors. Each function is represented as a 100-dimensional vector. Operands are filtered (MEM for memory addresses, IMM for large immediate values) to reduce vocabulary size. Function embeddings are composed via a self-attentive neural network with GRU cells, truncating functions at 150 instructions, covering over 90% of the training corpus. This allows us to directly compare CFG-based embeddings against whole-function embeddings in downstream tasks.

4.2. Model Training and Validation

This phase receives the binaries resulting from the Data Pre-processing phase and leverages an embedding model to train a binary classifier based on GNNs. The extraction function E of Equation (1) is implemented by a Python module that uses Radare2 APIs [30] to disassemble each binary, produce a dictionary F , and map the function names to their corresponding memory addresses. Then, we use `angr` to perform symbolic execution to reconstruct the CFG of each function. During this symbolic execution step, `angr` deals with loops and over-approximates the addresses that are targets of jumps for us. More precisely, we use the `angr` CFG reconstruction algorithm with the following parameters:

- *calldepth* equal to 2: this means that `angr` analyzes the current function and its direct calls up to two levels deep;

- *context sensitivity level* to 2: this parameter instructs `angr` to consider different calling contexts for functions for precise behavior analysis;
- *normalize* flag set to true: `angr` simplifies the CFG structure by removing unnecessary nodes and edges;
- *keep state* flag set to true: `angr` preserves all input states during analysis for debugging and exploration.

Subsequently, still using `angr`, we retrieve the assembly instructions of the basic blocks and we use an embedding model, either Asm2Vec or SAFE, to compute an embedding vector of 20 features to be associated with each node. Thus, the ACFGs keep the original CFGs' structure, but each node includes numerical features extracted from the assembly code. Finally, we format these labeled ACFGs as required by PyTorch Geometric's Graph Neural Network framework [31].

The training of the GNN employs a grid search with cross-validation to select the optimal model configuration, with a focus on minimizing data leakage and overfitting. This training process is described in Algorithm 1. To prevent potential data leakage from the validation set into the training set, we separate the training and validation sets by assigning all binaries derived from compiling the same library exclusively to one of these sets. Formally, given a dataset D , let S_0, S_1, \dots, S_k represent sets of binaries, where each S_i includes all and only the binaries resulting from the compilation of the same library, e.g., S_i is the set of all the binaries resulting from the compilation of PicoHTTP. During cross-validation, we select S_i as the validation set and train the model on all other sets S_j for $j \neq i$. This split is implemented in lines 9-10 of Algorithm 1 and ensures that each binary is held out for validation once.

We conduct a hyperparameter grid search to identify the optimal model configuration, leveraging the cross-validation splits for evaluation. In each fold i , the model is trained on the training set $\mathcal{D}_{\text{train}}$ and evaluated on the validation set \mathcal{D}_{val} based on the mean *recall* across all splits (lines 9-13 of Algorithm 1). In particular, we use recall as the primary performance metric,

Algorithm 1 Grid Search with Cross-Validation Training

```
1: Input: dataset  $D$ , parameter_grid, metric
2: Output: best_model
3: best_score  $\leftarrow -\infty$ 
4: best_params  $\leftarrow$  None
5: for params in parameter_grid do
6:   model  $\leftarrow$  initialize_model(params)
7:   total_score  $\leftarrow$  0
8:   for each fold  $i$  in the cross-validation splits do
9:      $\mathcal{D}_{\text{train}} \leftarrow \bigcup_{j \neq i} S_j$  (training set for fold  $i$ )
10:     $\mathcal{D}_{\text{val}} \leftarrow S_i$  (validation set for fold  $i$ )
11:    model.fit( $\mathcal{D}_{\text{train}}$ )
12:    score  $\leftarrow$  model.score( $\mathcal{D}_{\text{val}}$ )
13:    total_score  $\leftarrow$  total_score + score
14:   end for
15:   mean_score  $\leftarrow$  total_score / number of folds
16:   if mean_score > best_score then
17:     best_score  $\leftarrow$  mean_score
18:     best_params  $\leftarrow$  params
19:     best_model  $\leftarrow$  model
20:   end if
21: end for
22: return best_model
```

following standard practices in binary function analysis literature [6, 32]. The best model is the one with the highest mean recall computed by the grid search across all CV splits (lines 16–19). We then retrain the model on the combined training and validation sets to fine-tune its weights.

During the optimization process, we utilize the Adam optimizer and a loss function specifically designed to address class imbalance. Specifically, we use *Weighted Cross-Entropy Loss* [33], which assigns higher penalties to misclassified samples from the minority class (i.e., parser functions). In addition, we adopt a *Weighted Random Sampler* [34] to increase the probability of selecting minority class samples in each batch. Together, these techniques balance the influence of positive and negative classes during training, helping the model better capture parser functions. The final model is then used in the inference phase (see Section 4.3), where the softmax function provides predicted probabilities.

4.3. Model Inference Phase

This phase enables users to detect potential parser functions inside a binary and it is facilitated through a web application. This application includes two main components: a back-end and a front-end. The back-end processes the uploaded binary files and executes the steps described in the lower part of Figure 3: it extracts the functions from the binary, computes the CFG for each function (filtering out those with fewer than three nodes, as in the training process), enriches the nodes with the embeddings obtained from the selected embedding model, and creates the corresponding PyTorch Geometric Data. Finally, it queries the best model with this data and returns the probability of each function being a parser.

The front-end is a web application that allows users to upload binaries and displays the classification results in a tabular format, sorted by the probability of being a parser. In the resulting table, each row corresponds to a detected function and provides additional information, such as the number of nodes and edges in its CFG. The web interface also allows the display of the extracted CFGs from each function and the corresponding assembly code.

For example, Figure 4 shows the results of the analysis of the Jsmn executable, available in our repository [9]. For each function, this table contains its name, its address in the binary, the computed probabilities for being a “Parser” and a “Non-Parser”, and, in the column “Parser”, the predicted class determined using a 0.5 threshold. Additionally, the table reports the number of nodes and edges of its CFG, a graphical rendering of the graph, and its assembly code.

For Jsmn, ParserHunter identifies 11 functions, five of which are classified as “parser”, the others as “non-parser”. After selecting a candidate function, e.g., `jsmn_parse_primitive` among the three functions flagged as parsers, we may initiate a deeper security audit via `angr`-based symbolic execution. By selecting one of the buttons “CFGFast” or “CFGEmulated” [29] in the UI, ParserHunter generates a Python script template pre-filled with the code to reconstruct the CFG and set up symbolic variables to run advanced analysis. In the generated code, the user only needs to specify the address of the target function and any symbolic inputs before starting the symbolic execution by clicking on the “Run Code” button. At any point, the “Function Info” button can be used to print detailed CFG metadata, such as basic block addresses and their disassembled instructions. Figure 5 illustrates the process for the function at address `0x4005a7`, `jsmn_parse_primitive`.

To give an indication of runtime performance, we also measured the time required to analyze the Jsmn executable using SAFE embeddings. The three main phases took respectively 12.33 seconds for function extraction, 21.38 seconds for PyTorch Geometric data construction, and 5.09 seconds for model inference, resulting in a total of 38.81 seconds. These values closely match the observed wall-clock time, with only negligible overheads due to ancillary operations such as file handling.

5. Experimental Results

This section presents the evaluation of our approach, as obtained during the Model Training and Validation phase of ParserHunter. Our goal is to systematically assess the effectiveness and robustness of our method across different settings and to benchmark its performance against established baselines. Specifically, our experiments aim to determine the best-performing model based on recall, analyze the stability of predictions under varying compilation configurations, and provide representative examples of model decisions, including both correct classifications and errors. In addition, we compare our approach with other methods from the literature, including techniques based on large language models (LLMs), and perform an ablation study to demonstrate that both the GNN architecture and node features are crucial for achieving optimal performance. All

Show entries Search:

Name	Address	Parser	Probability not Parser	Probability Parser	Num Nodes	Num Edges	CFG	Assembly Code
sym.jsmn_parse	0x400a36	1	0.343	0.657	99	152		View Assembly Code
sym.jsmn_parse_string	0x40073f	1	0.357	0.643	50	81		View Assembly Code
sym.jsmn_parse_primitive	0x4005a7	1	0.362	0.638	34	52		View Assembly Code
sym.dump	0x400ff2	1	0.368	0.632	41	61		View Assembly Code
main	0x40127b	1	0.425	0.575	40	50		View Assembly Code
sym.realloc_it	0x400f92	0	0.656	0.344	10	10		View Assembly Code
entry.init0	0x4004f0	0	0.744	0.256	5	5		View Assembly Code
sym.__do_global_dtors_aux	0x4004c0	0	0.85	0.15	5	4		View Assembly Code
sym.deregister_tm_clones	0x400450	0	0.87	0.13	4	4		View Assembly Code
sym.register_tm_clones	0x400480	0	0.886	0.114	4	4		View Assembly Code

Showing 1 to 10 of 11 entries Previous 2 Next

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Figure 4: Web interface function table with predicted probabilities, CFG statistics, and assembly code.

experiments were conducted on a high-performance machine equipped with 4 Intel Xeon Gold 5218 CPUs (128 threads) and 1 TiB of RAM, running Ubuntu 22.04.4 LTS.

In summary, our experimental evaluation aims to answer the following research questions:

RQ1: What is the best-performing model for parser identification?

RQ2: How consistent are the model’s predictions across compilation variants, and how do compiler, architecture, and optimization level affect recall?

RQ3: How does our approach compare with existing approaches in the literature for parser identification?

RQ4: How does our approach compare with approaches based solely on binary function similarity?

RQ5: Ablation study: Are GNNs and code embedding necessary for effective parser identification?

RQ6: Can an LLM-based classifier outperform the GNN-based approach for parser identification across different code representations?

Table 3: Parameter settings and their considered values.

Parameter	Values
hidden_dim	[16, 32]
num_heads (GAT only)	[2, 4]
dropout	[0, 0.1]
learning_rate	[0.01, 0.1]
epochs	[10, 25]
batch_size	[32, 64]
weight_decay	[0.0, 0.01]

5.1. Best-performing model (RQ1)

To determine the best-performing model for parser identification, we evaluate which combination of GNN architecture and embedding model yields the best performance. More specifically, we consider four GNN architectures and two embedding models, exploring all possible pairings. As GNN architectures, we use Graph Attention Network (GAT) [13], Graph Convolutional Network (GCN) [12], GraphSage [14], and R-GCN [11], instantiated with only one relation type, all imple-

Run Python Code

```
import angr
import claripy

# Load the binary executable
binary_path = "./Binaries/temp_uploaded_file"
project = angr.Project(binary_path, auto_load_libs=False)

# Specify the address of the function you want to analyze
function_address = 0x4005a7 # Replace with your function's hex address

# Retrieve the function from the project's CFG
cfg = project.analyses.CFGEEmulated()
```

Delete

```
# Display function disassembly
print("Function Disassembly:")
for block in function.blocks:
    print(f"Block at address {hex(block.addr)}:")
    print(block.disassembly)
```

Delete

CFGFast
CFGEEmulated
Function Info
Symbolic Execution
+
Run Code

Output:

```
Analyzing function at address: 0x4005a7
Function Disassembly:
Block at address 0x4005a7:
0x4005a7:    push  rbp
0x4005a8:    mov   rbp, rsp
```

Figure 5: Web interface launching angr based analysis for a selected function.

mented in the PyTorch Geometric library [31]. Each architecture consists of two graph layers interleaved with ReLU activations, followed by a global sum pooling layer. For embeddings, we consider Asm2Vec and SAFE.

As detailed in Section 4.2, we adopt a leave-one-program-out evaluation protocol and perform hyperparameter optimization through grid search. The search explores the range of values reported in Table 3, which were selected both to reflect common configurations in the literature and to ensure a sufficiently broad search space. Models are then evaluated using two metrics: *recall* and *ROC-AUC* (Receiver Operating Characteristic Area Under the Curve). Table 4 and Table 5 report the results obtained by the cross-validation procedure on all possible pairings of architectures and embeddings. Each row corresponds to a validation library, with the remaining libraries used for training. The final row summarizes the average metric scores across all binaries for each combination. The results highlight the superiority of the GraphSAGE architecture, particularly when combined with the SAFE embedding model. Indeed, in this case, GraphSAGE achieves a mean recall of 0.92, which is higher than that of the other architectures. Crucially, GraphSAGE also produces more stable results, with a standard deviation of 0.09. The best-performing model returned by the grid search is GraphSAGE with SAFE embeddings.

We also provide qualitative insights on how this model behaves by inspecting a *correct prediction*, a *false negative*, and an *ambiguous case*. We take three representative functions of

the library Packcc under a *standard GCC compilation*.² According to Table 4 and Table 5, when Packcc is used as a validation parser by our cross-validation procedure, the GraphSAGE model achieves recall = 1 and ROC-AUC = 0.67. We consider three cases:

- *Correct prediction*: `is_valid_utf8_string` (true = 1, pred = 1). This function validates UTF-8 encoding by reconstructing code points and verifying encoding rules. The model correctly identifies it as a parser.
- *False negative*: `parse_rule` (true = 1, pred = 0). This function parses identifiers and constructs rule nodes, but is misclassified as a non-parser.
- *Ambiguous case*: `remove_leading_blanks` (true = 0, pred = 1). This function strips whitespace without returning a decision. Even human annotators may find this classification ambiguous, highlighting the difficulty in distinguishing between borderline cases.

All logs and detailed predictions are available in our online repository [9]. In summary, our answer to **RQ1** is:

²“Standard GCC compilation” refers to the default build with an optimization level equal to `-O0`.

Answer to RQ1:

The best-performing model uses the GraphSAGE architecture and the SAFE embedding. It reaches a mean recall of 0.92. It is trained with the following hyperparameters: *batch size 64, dropout 0.1, epochs 10, hidden dimension 16, input dimension 100, learning rate 0.1, output dimension 2, and weight decay 0.01.*

Answer to RQ2:

Our best-performing model demonstrates robustness across compilation variants. Recall remains stable across optimization settings for both x86-32 and x86-64 architectures. However, compiler choice has a measurable impact: with Clang, the model consistently achieves higher recall than with GCC.

5.2. Robustness under different compilations (RQ2)

We evaluate the prediction robustness of the best model under various compilations of the same functions, using different compilers and optimization levels. To evaluate the consistency of predictions across compilation variants, each function f in the validation library was compiled under N different settings. For each compiled variant f_i , the best model C outputs a prediction, resulting in the set:

$$\mathcal{P}_f = \{C(f_1), C(f_2), \dots, C(f_N)\}.$$

We define the *prediction consistency* of function f as:

$$\text{Cons}(f) = \frac{\max_{c \in \mathcal{C}} |\{i \in \{1, \dots, N\} : C(f_i) = c\}|}{N},$$

i.e., the fraction of variants classified with the most frequent label. A consistency of 100% means that all compiled variants of f receive the same label.

Figure 6 shows the reverse cumulative distribution of consistency scores across all validation libraries. On average, more than 50% of functions are consistently classified in 91%–100% of their variants (see light purple average bar), with ELF_Parser and YACC_Calculator with the lowest consistency values. Roughly, 70% of functions achieve consistency between 81%–90%. These results suggest that the model is robust to compiler-induced variability and relies on intrinsic code features rather than superficial artifacts.

Moreover, we evaluated how recall varies across two CPU architectures (x86-32 and x86-64), two compilers (GCC and Clang), and multiple optimization levels. For the x86-32 architecture (Figure 7), recall remains stable across optimization settings: with GCC, the model achieves an average recall of 0.90 (std. deviation 0.05), while with Clang a recall of 0.94 (std. deviation 0.04). Similarly, for the x86-64 architecture (Figure 8), results are consistent across optimization levels. GCC reaches an average recall of 0.93 (std. deviation 0.04), while Clang achieves 0.96 (std. deviation 0.07). With Clang, not only does it outperform GCC in both architectures, but it also shows markedly lower variability. This analysis is limited to the 180 functions detected by angr across all 28 compilation settings, so results may differ when considering the full function set.

In summary, our answer to **RQ2** is:

5.3. Comparison with PIE (RQ3)

The seminal work by Cojocar et al. [2] is the only paper in the literature that we are aware of, which addresses the problem of identifying parser functions inside binaries. The paper proposes a heuristic-based classification approach that relies on six manually designed features and that does not exploit modern machine learning techniques. Briefly, it works as follows. The PIE method first extracts LLVM intermediate representation (LLVM IR) from each binary function and computes the following six numeric features:

- `switch_loop`: Number of loops containing switch statements or dispatch tables, often indicative of state-machine parsers.
- `br_fact`: Measures the maximum branching factor via data-flow analysis of conditional instructions, capturing hand-coded or lowered switch logic.
- `in_edges`: Counts the maximum number of incoming edges to a basic block, reflecting complex control-flow rejoining typical of parsing loops.
- `bb_cnt`: The number of basic blocks in the function, as large functions are often used for parsers in optimized or inlined code.
- `call_cnt`: Counts how many times a function is called, since frequently invoked parsing functions (e.g., tokenizers) may indicate parsing logic.
- `switch`: Identifies standalone switch statements or jump tables, which are common in complex input-handling code.

These features are combined into a score according to the following formula:

$$\text{score} = \sum_{f \in \text{Features}} w_f \frac{x_f - \min(X_f)}{\max(X_f) - \min(X_f)}.$$

Where x_f is the value of feature f for the function under analysis, and X_f is the set of values that feature f takes across all functions in the dataset. The normalization term ensures that each feature is scaled to a value between 0 and 1, keeping the overall score bounded. The parameter w_f denotes the weight assigned to feature f , with w_0, \dots, w_5 corresponding respectively to the six features described above. The computed score is assigned to each function: a function is classified as a parser if its score exceeds a given threshold T .

Table 4: Recall for GCN, GAT, GraphSAGE, and R-GCN architecture using Asm2Vec and Safe.

Dataset	Asm2Vec (Recall)				Safe (Recall)			
	GCN	GAT	GraphSAGE	R-GCN	GCN	GAT	GraphSAGE	R-GCN
PicoHTTPparser	0.79	0.75	0.74	0.78	0.67	0.85	0.86	0.83
CSimpleJSONParser	0.90	0.67	0.68	0.93	0.84	0.84	0.91	0.93
Benoitc_HTTP	0.94	0.90	0.89	1.00	0.76	0.94	1.00	1.00
CParserXML	0.78	0.64	0.90	0.80	0.56	0.71	0.98	0.60
cJSON_Parser	0.74	0.80	0.66	0.83	0.81	0.85	0.92	0.84
Yacc Calculator	1.00	0.89	0.82	0.82	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
PCAP Parser	0.76	0.92	0.92	1.00	0.60	0.89	1.00	1.00
Network-packet-analyzer	0.25	0.82	0.75	0.60	0.44	0.39	0.91	1.00
Packcc	0.85	0.77	0.94	0.82	0.75	0.92	1.00	0.95
ELF-parser	0.85	0.73	0.82	0.69	0.89	0.82	0.70	0.84
Mean	0.79	0.79	0.81	0.83	0.73	0.82	0.92	0.90
STD	0.19	0.09	0.10	0.12	0.16	0.17	0.09	0.11

Table 5: ROC-AUC for GCN, GAT, GraphSAGE, and R-GCN architecture using Asm2Vec and Safe.

Dataset	Asm2Vec (ROC-AUC)				Safe (ROC-AUC)			
	GCN	GAT	GraphSAGE	R-GCN	GCN	GAT	GraphSAGE	R-GCN
PicoHTTPparser	0.67	0.75	0.81	0.83	0.80	0.71	0.81	0.81
CSimpleJSONParser	0.76	0.78	0.76	0.78	0.80	0.78	0.80	0.78
Benoitc_HTTP	0.86	0.81	0.83	0.88	0.92	0.88	0.93	0.92
CParserXML	0.88	0.93	0.96	0.97	0.97	0.86	0.96	0.96
cJSON_Parser	0.70	0.80	0.69	0.79	0.79	0.75	0.83	0.82
Yacc Calculator	0.77	0.75	0.76	0.86	0.81	0.76	0.93	0.91
PCAP Parser	0.77	0.83	0.89	0.89	0.87	0.72	0.89	0.90
Network-packet-analyzer	0.66	0.82	0.70	0.74	0.60	0.63	0.66	0.63
Packcc	0.65	0.74	0.68	0.73	0.68	0.65	0.67	0.67
ELF-parser	0.60	0.65	0.61	0.69	0.65	0.59	0.68	0.70
Mean	0.73	0.78	0.77	0.82	0.79	0.73	0.82	0.81
STD	0.09	0.07	0.10	0.08	0.11	0.09	0.11	0.11

Here, we compare their methodology against our approach. Due to the lack of publicly available models and data from their experiments, we implement their approach from scratch and test it on our dataset. In our implementation, we do not rely on LLVM IR, but we use `angr` to extract VEX IR and Decompile C pseudo-code. Then, we compute the score above for each function using the same six features, deriving their values from the extracted code.

We then evaluate the classification performance of the PIE method on our dataset in three different experiments:

1. *Original weights*: We apply the score formula above using the original parameters used in the PIE paper: $T = 0.247$, $w_0 = 0.695$, $w_1 = 0.502$, $w_2 = 0.364$, $w_3 = 0.413$, $w_4 = 0.134$, $w_5 = 0.685$.
2. *Fine-tuned weights*: Since the parameter values reported in their paper were fine-tuned on a dataset that is not publicly available, we applied the PIE 2-fold cross-validation procedure to our dataset to derive optimal parameters specific to our evaluation setting. The resulting values were

$$T = 0.0917, w_0 = 0.077, w_1 = 0.391, w_2 = 0.131, w_3 = 0.106, w_4 = 0.214, w_5 = 0.077.$$

3. *ML-based classifier*: We replace the score-based heuristic approach with a supervised machine learning pipeline based on XGBoost. Each function was represented by the six numerical PIE features, which were used as input to the model. The features are first normalized using a `StandardScaler`, then we train the classifier using the grid search and the leave-one-program-out procedure described in Section 4.2, ensuring that the validation library remains unseen. The pipeline consists of a `StandardScaler` for feature normalization followed by an `XGBClassifier` with the best performing configuration using 50 estimators, maximum depth of 3, a learning rate of 0.1, and `logloss` as the evaluation metric. Performance is assessed in terms of recall.

Table 6 shows the recall values for all three experiments, including mean and standard deviation. The results show that their heuristic approach yields a low recall (0.41 in the best case

Figure 6: The figure shows the reverse cumulative distribution of the *prediction consistency* across all compilation settings for each validation parser. The x-axis indicates bins of *prediction consistency* (from highest to lowest), while the y-axis shows the cumulative fraction of functions that achieved at least that level of consistency. Each bar corresponds to the binary used as a validation set during the cross-validation experiments.

Figure 7: ParserHunter recall results for different optimization levels for x86-32 architecture

Figure 8: ParserHunter recall results for different optimization levels for x86-64 architecture

of Packcc), even with fine-tuned weights. The recall improves significantly with a simple XGBoost-based classifier (0.65 mean recall). However, our graph-based approach results in better performance (0.92 mean recall) with an improvement of 41.5%.

In conclusion, our answer to **RQ3** is:

Answer to RQ3:

Our best-performing model surpasses the PIE heuristic-based approach, achieving a higher mean recall. Overall, it improves recall by approximately 41.5% compared to the best-performing model based on the PIE heuristic.

5.4. Comparison with binary function similarity (RQ4)

Binary function similarity is the problem of taking as input the binary representation of a pair of functions, and producing a score that captures the similarity between them. It plays a crucial role in systems security because many tasks require measuring function similarity as a core building block. For example, binary code similarity enables reverse engineers to match functions in stripped, statically linked binaries with labeled counterparts in a database, greatly reducing the manual effort required for code understanding. Here, we follow a similar idea and develop a parser classifier based on binary function similarity, which we use as a baseline for comparison against our best model.

We leverage the pretrained SAFE model [16] to obtain a

Table 6: Recall of three PIE-based baselines: (i) original weights from the paper, (ii) fine-tuned weights on our dataset, and (iii) ML-based classifier.

Dataset	Original	Fine-tuned	XGBoost
	Weights	Weights	
PicoHTTPparser	0.06	0.33	0.55
CSimpleJSONParser	0.02	0.24	0.61
Benoitc_HTTP	0.11	0.08	0.90
CParserXML	0.01	0.12	0.59
cJSON_Parser	0.01	0.10	0.78
Yacc Calculator	0.00	0.06	0.79
PCAP Parser	0.00	0.01	0.50
Network-packet-analyzer	0.00	0.01	0.44
Packcc	0.13	0.41	0.60
ELF-parser	0.03	0.18	0.70
Mean	0.04	0.16	0.65
STD	0.04	0.13	0.14

100-dimensional embedding vector for each function in our dataset after extracting their assembly code through `angr`. Similarly to the procedure described in Section 4.2, all programs are taken as a reference database (analogous to the training set), and k -Nearest Neighbors (KNN) with cosine similarity as recommended in [16], is used to assign labels to a new input program (analogous to the test-validation set) with a majority class assignment. This setup enables a direct comparison of the results of this procedure, as shown in Table 7, with our previously reported results. We evaluated KNN with values of k equal to 1, 3, and 5, and consistently observed that smaller values of k yield higher recall. Additional results for more values of k are available in our shared repository [9]. Table 7 reports the recall values obtained from these experiments, with the best performance achieved for $k = 1$. However, our approach, which is tailored to the specific task of identifying parsing functions, results in better mean recall with an improvement of 27.7%.

In conclusion, our answer to **RQ4** is:

Answer to RQ4:

Our best-performing model outperforms the approach based on binary function similarity, achieving a higher mean recall. Specifically, it improves recall by approximately 27.7% compared to their best-performing configuration.

5.5. Ablation Study (RQ5)

We conduct an ablation study to demonstrate that the combination of GNNs and code embedding models is essential for achieving the performance of our best-performing model, as reported in Section 5.1. To assess the specific contribution of the GNN component, we trained two alternative classifiers: one based on XGBoost and the other on a neural network. Both models take as input the numerical SAFE embeddings computed for each function.

The training procedure for both models follows the same framework described in Section 4.2, where one program is left

Table 7: Recall of SAFE embeddings using KNN classifier with k set to 1, 3, and 5.

Dataset	KNN Recall		
	K=1	K=3	K=5
PicoHTTPparser	0.79	0.76	0.61
CSimpleJSONParser	0.60	0.55	0.08
Benoitc_HTTP	0.89	0.90	0.82
CParserXML	0.50	0.48	0.37
cJSON_Parser	0.75	0.76	0.64
Yacc Calculator	0.72	0.72	0.00
PCAP Parser	0.71	0.71	0.10
Network-packet-analyzer	0.62	0.62	0.01
Packcc	0.78	0.78	0.48
ELF-parser	0.88	0.88	0.77
Mean	0.72	0.71	0.39
STD	0.11	0.12	0.30

Table 8: Performance comparison of XGBoost and a Neural Network Classifier (NNC) across different metrics using the Safe embeddings.

Dataset	Recall		ROC-AUC	
	XGBoost	NNC	XGBoost	NNC
PicoHTTPparser	0.61	0.61	0.85	0.87
CSimpleJSONParser	0.27	0.17	0.77	0.81
Benoitc_HTTP	0.82	0.95	0.93	0.92
CParserXML	0.36	0.36	0.94	0.93
cJSON_Parser	0.60	0.65	0.81	0.86
Yacc Calculator	0.65	0.65	0.70	0.68
PCAP Parser	0.00	0.00	0.82	0.91
Network-packet-analyzer	0.00	0.00	0.54	0.60
Packcc	0.47	0.45	0.61	0.62
ELF-parser	0.74	0.83	0.71	0.75
Mean	0.45	0.47	0.77	0.80
STD	0.29	0.33	0.13	0.12

out as the validation set and the remaining programs are used for training (leave-one-program-out cross-validation). A grid search is performed to identify the optimal hyperparameter configuration, and recall is used to evaluate the performance. The best-performing neural network configuration utilizes a hidden dimension of 32, a dropout rate of 0.01, 25 training epochs, a batch size of 64, and a learning rate of 0.1. For the XGBoost model, the optimal configuration employs 50 estimators, a maximum depth of 10, and a learning rate of 0.1.

The recall values obtained in these experiments are in Table 8. The results show that the neural network-based classifier consistently outperforms the XGBoost-based classifier in terms of mean recall, with a similar trend observed when the ROC-AUC metric is considered. Nevertheless, when comparing the neural network-based classifier (0.47 mean recall) with our best-performing model (0.92 mean recall), the latter consistently achieves superior performance.

A second experiment aims to quantify the contribution of the code embeddings to the classification. To this end, we mod-

ified our GNN architectures by assigning a constant value of 1 to each node’s feature, rather than its embedding vector. This forces the model to rely exclusively on the raw CFG structure without access to the semantic information typically encoded in the embeddings. We repeat the training procedure described in Section 4.2, performing a grid search over the hyperparameter values reported in Table 3 and evaluating performance using the recall metric. The results, summarized in Table 9, indicate that models trained without node embeddings suffer a substantial decline in performance. In particular, the best model in this setting (GraphSAGE) achieves a mean recall of 0.50, whereas the best-performing model (GraphSAGE) of Section 5.1 achieves a mean recall of 0.92. These results confirm that node features in the form of code embeddings contribute to parser detection. While CFG structure provides valuable topological information, embeddings capture complementary semantic properties that are essential for achieving high recall.

In conclusion, our answer to **RQ5** is:

Answer to RQ5:

The ablation study confirms that integrating both structural and semantic information is crucial for accurate parser detection. In fact, our model achieves a mean recall of 0.92, outperforming the simple neural network classifier (0.47) and the GraphSAGE with constant node features (0.50). This corresponds to a relative improvement of about 95.7% and 84%, respectively.

5.6. Comparison with LLM classification approaches (RQ6)

We aim to evaluate whether an LLM-based classifier can outperform a GNN-based classifier tailored for parser identification. We consider three freely available LLMs for our experiments: Mistral, codellama:34b, and qwen3-coder:30b. For comparability with the GNN evaluation protocol (Section 4.2), each model is asked to output a single binary label, 1 for parser functions and 0 otherwise, using the same decision criteria described in Table 1 (the full prompt used is in Appendix A).

To study the robustness of LLM predictions across different program representations, we test each model using three forms of code extracted with `angr`: assembly, VEX IR, and decompiled high-level code. Table 10 reports the mean recall aggregated per program, divided by LLM and input representation. Before computing recall, we exclude predictions that are not valid binary answers. Such invalid cases arise for two reasons: (i) `angr` cannot extract high-code representation for the function, making it impossible for the LLM to produce any prediction; and (ii) even if the code was extracted and it is available, the LLM cannot provide a binary decision (0 or 1), typically because it expresses uncertainty or provides a non-committal answer. These predictions are omitted from the recall computation since they are neither correct nor incorrect.

Regarding missing code, decompiled high-level representations are the most affected: `angr` fails to recover decompiled code for approximately 862 functions (approximately 10% of all functions), reflecting the known limitations of binary lifting due to compilation-induced information loss. Assembly

and VEX IR extractions are significantly more reliable for all functions in our dataset. Across the evaluated LLMs, Mistral exhibits the highest mean recall, with its best performance achieved on decompiled code. Interestingly, decompiled high-level code generally leads to higher recall across models. This can be attributed to the fact that, when successfully recovered, decompiled code provides a more readable and structured view of a function, making it easier for both humans and LLMs to understand. In contrast, low-level code representations, such as assembly or VEX IR, are more difficult to understand and reason about due to their reduced abstraction and unstructured control-flow, which can pose a challenge to general-purpose language models.

In summary, while LLMs show promising capabilities and benefit from higher-level code inputs, their recall remains lower than that of a dedicated GNN classifier, indicating that LLMs alone are not yet sufficient for reliable parser identification.

In conclusion, the answer to **RQ6** is:

Answer to RQ6:

The GNN model achieves a higher recall compared to the best LLM-performing model, corresponding to an improvement of roughly 21%. Moreover, LLM-based models sometimes fail to provide a definitive answer (0 or 1) as requested in the prompt, instead expressing uncertainty or offering a non-committal response.

6. Related Work

Parser and validation functions are fundamental components in software systems because they process external input. To the best of our knowledge, only the seminal work by Cojocar et al. [2] has addressed the problem of identifying parser functions inside binaries. The paper highlights the inherent vulnerabilities in embedded parsers, which are often optimized for performance and size but lack rigorous input validation, thereby making the firmware of embedded systems susceptible to memory corruption attacks. They propose a methodology to identify parser functions that relies on six manually extracted features from datasets of parser implementations built using `lex`, `yacc`, and custom open-source firmware. These features form the basis for a heuristic-based classification approach that does not utilize modern machine learning techniques, and the generalization capabilities and performance of this approach are unclear. In contrast, our methodology does not rely on manually engineered features but leverages recent advances in deep learning, specifically embedding models (`Asm2Vec`, `SAFE`) and GNNs to provide a more general and adaptable approach. Furthermore, we adopt a broader notion of parsers and formalize it so that any function satisfying the requirements listed in Table 1 is included. To support further research and facilitate comparisons, we construct and publicly release a dataset that encompasses not only parsers for textual data, such as XML and JSON, but also for binary data, including ELF and network packets. Another important difference between our work and

Table 9: Performance comparison of GCN, GAT, GraphSAGE, and R-GCN across different metrics with all node features set to 1.

Dataset	Recall				ROC-AUC			
	GCN	GAT	GraphSAGE	R-GCN	GCN	GAT	GraphSAGE	R-GCN
PicoHTTPparser	0.81	0.00	0.27	0.0	0.84	0.59	0.84	0.83
CSimpleJSONParser	0.74	0.00	0.11	0.11	0.80	0.56	0.77	0.78
Benoitc_HTTP	0.13	0.00	0.66	0.66	0.93	0.34	0.93	0.93
CParserXML	0.07	0.00	0.39	0.25	0.97	0.35	0.97	0.97
cJSON_Parser	0.29	0.00	0.49	0.51	0.86	0.60	0.85	0.85
Yacc Calculator	0.72	0.00	0.86	0.82	0.87	0.74	0.86	0.87
PCAP Parser	0.01	0.00	1.00	0.0	0.88	0.79	0.93	0.93
Network-packet-analyzer	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.0	0.50	0.56	0.60	0.60
Packcc	0.12	0.00	0.52	0.52	0.64	0.56	0.65	0.65
ELF-parser	0.82	1.00	0.73	0.44	0.74	0.35	0.74	0.73
Mean	0.37	0.10	0.50	0.33	0.80	0.54	0.81	0.81
STD	0.34	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.13	0.14	0.11	0.11

Table 10: Summary of recall performance and prediction coverage for three LLMs across three input representations.

Metric	Mistral			codellama:34b			qwen3-coder:30b		
	Decompiled	VEX IR	Assembly	Decompiled	VEX IR	Assembly	Decompiled	VEX IR	Assembly
Mean Recall	0.76	0.47	0.75	0.57	0.52	0.54	0.58	0.19	0.58
Std Recall	0.15	0.10	0.20	0.08	0.08	0.10	0.21	0.17	0.28
% not valid predictions	11%	8%	2%	21%	38%	20%	11%	0.8%	0.4%

that of Cojocar et al. [2] lies in the tooling: whereas their approach relies on proprietary disassembly software, we rely on open-source tools such as angr. In addition, the absence of publicly available models and data from their experiments prevents us from using their setup as a baseline for comparison; instead, we conduct our evaluations on the dataset we created, showing that our approach achieves a higher mean recall.

Our research is also related to the growing body of literature utilizing data-driven binary analysis methods. Most papers in this research line use machine learning to achieve two tasks: vulnerability detection and binary function similarity. In this field, several approaches and techniques have been proposed. We focus only on works that are more similar to ours, namely those that consider graph representations of programs, embedding-based techniques, and graph-oriented deep learning models. We refer the interested reader to the relevant literature reviews [35, 6] for an overview of the various proposals. The primary difference between the works discussed below and ours lies in the ML task to be solved.

Concerning the first task, Aumpansub and Huang [36] address the problem of detecting vulnerabilities in off-the-shelf software in which only the binary code is available. The methodology relies on the SARD dataset [37], which is widely used as a testbed for detecting vulnerabilities in source code, to label the training data at the function level. They first compile the various programs of the dataset, disassemble the resulting code, compute its CFG, and derive a set of features using syntactical information of the retrieved assembly instructions. Then, they train two classifiers based on BLSTM and BGRU deep learning

models to detect vulnerabilities.

VulANalyzeR [38] is a deep learning-based model for an explainable and automated vulnerability detection and CWE classification tool. This tool disassembles a program to extract its CFG and its instructions; the instructions are then processed to learn their vector representation through an LSTM model; the various learned vectors are aggregated with the information about the CFG, and a graph representation is learned through a GNN. The learned graph is then processed by a specific aggregation mechanism to explain the model results and locate the vulnerability. The methodology is similar to ours in that we extract features from binaries, use an embedding mechanism to have a vector representation of assembly instructions, and build a GNN model for classification. However, our task differs, and we provide only a binary answer (parser vs non-parser function). Similarly, BinVulDet [39] detects vulnerabilities in binaries. BinVulDet first decompiles the binaries to obtain their pseudocodes, then extracts the statements related to vulnerability through a program-slicing algorithm, and assembles them into code gadgets. These gadgets are normalized and transformed into vectors. Finally, a BiLSTM-attention neural network is trained to generate vector representations of vulnerability patterns and classify them to detect whether target codes contain vulnerabilities. In contrast, our work directly operates on binary code to extract features and train a GNN model.

Concerning binary similarity, Xu et al. [40] propose a deep neural network approach that generates function embeddings tailored for this task. For each function, they extract its CFG enriched with node-level attributes and apply a graph-embedding

network to produce a fixed-size representation. Their method leverages a Siamese architecture, ensuring that embeddings of equivalent functions (i.e., binaries compiled from the same source) are mapped to nearby points in the embedding space, while the embeddings of inequivalent functions are positioned farther apart. To train this Siamese network, despite limited ground truth labels, they assume that functions stemming from the same source code are similar and all others are dissimilar, allowing the creation of large labeled pairs without extensive manual annotation. Applying this pairwise framework to parser identification introduces a significant annotation challenge: training a Siamese network requires labeled similarity scores for every function pair, leading to a quadratic labeling effort as the dataset grows. By contrast, our method assigns a single binary label (parser vs. non-parser) to each function, greatly reducing the manual labeling burden and directly focusing on the parser-identification task.

SAFE [41] uses a self-attentive embedding network for binary code that converts a disassembled function into a fixed-size vector. For each function under consideration, first, SAFE embeds individual instructions via a skip-gram (“i2v”) model, then it processes the instruction sequence through a self-attentive Bi-RNN to generate the final embedding of the function. SAFE is trained to map functions compiled from the same source code to similar vectors in the embedding space. While their work focuses on the problem of “same-source” code similarity, our objective is to distinguish parser from non-parser behavior. To this end, we introduce an identification pipeline specific for this task that relies on the pretrained SAFE model for computing the embedding for node features. Moreover, the experiments of Section 5 show that our model outperforms the approach based on binary function similarity, achieving a higher mean recall.

An advanced graph-matching neural network with enhanced attention is proposed by Zhao et al. [42] for detecting homologous vulnerabilities. The approach addresses structural variations resulting from different compilation configurations by focusing on critical semantic information and structural differences within functions.

While the papers above focus on detecting specific vulnerabilities or estimating function similarities, our work addresses the different task of identifying potential parser functions, serving as a preliminary step for subsequent vulnerability analysis. Similar to the above papers, we exploit graph representation techniques and embedding models to automatically extract features from disassembled binary functions. In contrast, we do not rely on fixed graph-matching techniques, as parser functions can be implemented in infinitely diverse ways. Instead, we leverage GNNs to classify functions based on graph representations, offering a flexible and scalable solution to the problem of parser function identification.

7. Conclusion

This paper presented a novel methodology and the tool ParserHunter for identifying parsing functions within binary executables. Our methodology relied on a set of well-defined criteria

that a parser-like function must meet and consisted of the following steps. First, we extracted all the functions from a binary, computed their CFGs, and enriched them with features computed by an embedding model to capture semantic information on the function’s behavior. These ACFGs serve as the input for the training phase, based on GNNs, to build a binary classifier. Additionally, we implemented our methodology into a practical tool usable through a web interface and demonstrated its effectiveness through an experimental evaluation, which included a cross-validation step, on ten real-world binaries. Also, ParserHunter not only enables users to identify parsing functions within binaries but also provides features to accommodate the security auditing of the identified functions through symbolic execution.

While the results of the cross-validation step validate the efficacy and generalizability of the approach, some limitations remain, which are an interesting area for future work. A first limitation concerns the manual effort required for labeling the dataset used in training. In this paper, the authors served as annotators, assigning labels to each function in the dataset. Clearly, this manual annotation is prone to errors and may introduce biases that affect the training and evaluation phases. To address such a limitation, we plan to investigate methods to automate the labeling process, such as incorporating a pseudo-labeling technique or semi-supervised learning. Developing a robust auto-labeling framework will make the methodology more scalable and adaptable to diverse datasets. A second limitation of the current work is that we assign the same importance to the requirements in Table 1 and require a function to satisfy them to be assigned to the parser class. However, there could be some functions that partially meet our requirements and could be an interesting target for security auditing. To address this limitation, we plan to assign a weight to each requirement, ranging from 0 to 1, representing its level of satisfaction, and to adapt our pipeline to incorporate these considerations. Moreover, to better address the last requirement on composition, we plan to also consider information about the call graph of the program. Another interesting future direction can be to study a hybrid architecture that combines GNNs and LLMs to classify parser functions. Finally, we aim to explore additional situations and tasks arising in the field of binary analysis, particularly those involving complex and obfuscated binaries, to push the boundaries of our tool’s capabilities and validate its robustness in these scenarios as well.

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Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used Grammarly and ChatGPT for grammar and spelling checks. After

using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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Appendix A. LLM Prompt Templates

This appendix reports the generalized prompt template used to query the LLMs during the parser–non-parser classification task described in Section 5. The prompt enforces a strictly binary output (0 or 1) and includes the same set of classification requirements presented in Table 1. The only difference between queries is the code representation provided to the model, which can be assembly, VEX IR, or decompiled high-level code.

You are a binary analysis assistant.
I will give you the code of a function
Your task is to classify whether the function is
a PARSER function or not based on the following requirements:

Classification requirements:
<INSERT REQUIREMENTS>

Your output MUST follow these strict rules:

- Output ONLY a single character:
 - '1' if the function satisfies ALL requirements
 - or at least the final one (Composition).
- Output '0' if the function does NOT satisfy the criteria.
- NO explanations.
- NO extra text.
- NO formatting. Only '0' or '1'.

Function code:
<INSERT FUNCTION CODE>

Prediction (ONLY '0' or '1'):